

E-Marketing – A Global Perspective

Dr.D.Muthusamy

*Head of the Department & Associate Professor
PG and Research Department of Commerce
Kurinji College Arts & Science, Trichy*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Muthusamy, D & Shoba,
N. “E-Marketing – A
Global Perspective.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 6, no. S1, 2018,
pp. 45–49.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2532937](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2532937)

N.Shoba

*Ph.D Research Scholar, PG and Research Department of Commerce
Kurinji College Arts & Science, Trichy*

Abstract

E-commerce provides the capability of buying and selling goods, information and services on the Internet and other online surroundings. Online Marketing includes identify unmet needs, producing goods and services to meet those need and pricing, distributing and promoting those goods and service to produce a profit. Purchaser relationship management worked as a tool increased use of e-commerce makes CRM a necessary component. E-marketing perform a function within Short period of time.. Questions are related to E-Marketing in which given options are Agree, Disagree, Strongly disagree, Strongly agree, Neutral, it is basic necessity of e-marketing are liveness, effectiveness of work, provide the better security of e- paying their taxes, licenses, fees etc. In future e-marketing provide the efficient website

Introduction

E - Commerce and E-marketing

It is based on the online point of view of the conducted business E-commerce provides the capability of buying and selling goods, information and services on the Internet and other online surroundings .Internet marketing as “the process of building and maintaining purchaser relationships through online activities to facilitate the exchange of ideas, goods and services that satisfy the goals of both parties. It is a mixture of all the activities of advertising, promotion publicity deciding the look and feel of the product, how it will be sold and sent to the purchaser etc

E-Marketing Defined

Marketing is the management process responsible for identifying, anticipating and satisfying purchasers.

Identifying - The Internet be used for marketing research to find out purchasers needs and wants.

Anticipating - The Internet provides an additional channel by which purchasers can access information and make purchases.

Satisfying - A key success factor in e-marketing is achieving purchaser satisfaction through the electronic channel, this raises issues such as is the site easy to use, does it adequately.

CRM(Purchaser Relationship Management)

E-commerce and Purchaser Relationship Management (CRM) jointly worked as a tool. E-commerce mainly target purchasers by getting closer to purchasers, serving them better, cost cutting, introducing new goods and services and creating new opportunities through the Internet.

- Purchaser's interaction or satisfaction
- Convenience
- Speed of processing the transaction through e-response

E-Marketing Methods

1) Search Engine Market (SEM)

Search engine marketing (SEM), which allows firms to aim consumers by placing ads on search engines, has confirmed to be an effective audience gaining strategy.

- Pay-Per Click
- Search Engine Optimization(SEO)

2) Online PR

PR stands for "public relations". Online PR is organization publicity about an organization and its brand, goods or web sites through its online presence and third party web sites and other digital media.

- Link-building and generating editorial
- Blogs, communities and RSS
- Handling how your brand is presented on third party sites

3) E-Mail Marketing

Email marketing is a method of distributing information about product or service or for soliciting feedback from purchaser about a product or service through Email. Email addresses of purchasers and prospective purchaser may be collected or purchased. Special deals and postcard by e-mail marketing Increase profit and sales, encourage goods and services, last minute special offer. The two variables are used by e-mails Opt-in email

- Opt – out email

4) Hanging Advertisement

Hanging is a placement of ads on website for a fee. The offline comparable of this form of online marketing would be traditional ads on newspaper or magazines.

- Hanging sand Button
- Rectangles and Pop-ups
- Skyscrapers

5) Viral Market

Viral marketing uses email to transmit a promotional message to another potential purchaser. It is very useful in reaching a large number of people rapidly like a computer internet.

6) Blog Market

It is an act of positioning comments, expressing opinions or making announcement in a discussion forum and can be accomplished .

Traditional market v/s E-market

E-Market	Traditional Market
It is very economical and fast way to encourage product	Traditional Marketing is very expensive and takes more time to encourage product

It is very useful for promoting product globally[without any additional cost]	It is very expensive and time consuming process for traditional marketing
In E- Marketing, you can also work with less workers. [you can take more work with less manpower].	In Traditional Marketing, you need more workers with more man power which in terms requires spending lot of money

Traditional vs. Internet Marketing Mix

The internet-marketing mixes essentially the same as the marketing mix. It is simply the adaptation of price, place, product and promotion to the internet-marketing context.

The 4 P internet-Marketing Mix (P)-The basic function for Exchange Table

Marketing Mix Elements (P)	Description
Product	diversity, quality, intend feature, brand name, packaging, sizes, services, warranties, and returns.
Price	List,price,discounts, allowances, payment period, and credit terms.
Promotion	Advertisement, selling, sales advertising public relations, and direct marketing
Place	Channels, coverage, assortments, locations, inventory, transportations and logistics

Steps to Start E-Marketing

- a) Building Effecting Website
- b) Designing Compelling Messages
- c) Sending strategic newsletters
- d) Online Advertising
- e) Managing purchaser database

Benefits of E-marketing

- a) Extremely low risk
- b) Reduction in costs through automation and. use of electronic media
- c) Faster response to both marketers and the. end user
- d) Increased ability to measure and collect data
- e) Opens the possibility to a market of one through personal

Limitations of E-marketing

- a) Dependability on technology
- b) Security, privacy issues
- c) Maintenance costs due to a constantly evolving surroundings

Objectives of the e-marketing

- a) Methods of making market more effective and fulfill the needs and requirements of the purchasers.
- b) To Conduct research as to the nature e.g demographics, preference and needs of existing and potential purchasers.
- c) Designing processes to provide a strong communication between businessman and clients.
- d) To Identify the area of quality purchaser service with personal attention.

Problem Formulation

Despite different types of relationship between marketing and purchasers. There is a need to know that still the people residing in small cities and large cities. People have significant relationship with their marketing. It has been well recognized that large city population prefer Online marketing to a greater extend as compared to their small cities counterparts.

Difference in Socio Economic Backgrounds

Research Methodology

This study on data collection from the secondary sources. Primary data also collected through questionnaire based on online users, satisfaction of consumer level rating scale of online buyers. The secondary data sources including websites, newspapers, various published and unpublished article about pre-primary education etc.

Collection of data through questionnaire

In this method a suppliers is sent to the person concerned with request to answer the questions and return the suppliers. A feedback form consists of a number of questions printed or typed in a definite order on a form or set of forms. The questionnaire is mailed to respondent who are expected to read and understand the question .The and write down the reply in the space meant for the purpose in questionnaire itself. The customer to have answer the questions on their own. The research method on on-line marketing is based on the survey. Objective type questions have been designed in survey.

Sr. No.	Questions	Satisfied	Not satisfied	Highly satisfied	Highly not satisfied	Neutral
1	retort service is available for all questionnaire in e-marketing	52	0	30	0	18
2	Can we sell personal objects through e-marketing	48	0	32	8	12
3	Is this through marketing	42	0	38	9	11
4	Internet marketing requires a great deal of pains of hard work	52	8	18	6	16

5	Search engine is the best system for online marketing	48	7	22	8	15
6	Is it can be both helpful and risk to your business at the same time	47	6	32	5	14
7	Do traditional market save the time	20	28	22	18	12
8	Is your item for consumption available local or worldwide	35	4	45	0	16
9	Chances of making mistakes In Online marketing	36	7	15	3	39
10	Is this a reliable service	45	0	33	2	20

Conclusion

On-line marketing has become an integral part of modern Marketing. This opportunities on-line marketing operation increases different levels of risks for marketing. More than several Years of Internet marketing research have yielded a set of important findings. It is clear that the net is playing a more and more important role in the field of marketing. Marketers and their end-users are becoming aware of the need to measure the collaborative effects of marketing (i.e., how the Internet affects in-store sales). In Mansa The study reveals that purchasers do-not use of e-marketing. They do- not have any knowledge of e-marketing. Some learn have been designed on survey .The respondent have to answer the questions on their own. Some peoples satisfies on our views. But some peoples were not satisfies with us. Respondent have sufficient to give well thought out answers. Respondents, who are not easily not rechable,can besides be reached conveniently. This study states that Online marketing System provides greater reach to purchasers. Feedback can be get easily as internet is virtual in nature. Purchaser loyalty can be gain. Personal attention can be given by market to purchaser also quality service can be served. We came to know various strengths of Online marketing system such as quality purchaser service, greater reach, time saving purchaser loyalty, easy access to information, 24 hours access, reduce manual work ,no need to carry cash easy online applications etc.